

ML-Based Wheat Production Estimation using Two Decades of Remote Sensing & Meteorological Time-Series Data across Five Major Indian States

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ABSTRACT

Estimating production prior to harvest is a crucial practice that enables both the government and farmers to manage the harvest process effectively. This study focuses on predicting wheat production in five states of India by integrating satellite-derived data with machine learning techniques. The temporal coverage of the study extends from 2003 to 2025, incorporating crop production statistics and meteorological parameters from visual crossing collected during the peak wheat growth window in its phenological cycle, i.e., from November to March. Terra MODIS data products such as NDVI, LAI and thermal anomaly, along with soil moisture from GLDAS, were obtained. For classifying wheat and non-wheat areas, decision-rule based thresholding was applied to NDVI values. Subsequently, wheat production was predicted using tree-based ML algorithms, such as Decision Tree Regressor (DTR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), Extra Trees Regressor (ETR), and XGBoost Regressor (XGBR). The models' performances were compared using evaluation metrics and plots. The findings demonstrated the superior performance of XGBR over all others. The average error percentages for the DTR, RFR, ETR and XGBR models were 10.3%, 8.3%, 7.4%, and 5.6%, respectively. For validation, the predicted production was compared with the production statistics on UPAg. Comparison with official production statistics confirmed the robustness and reliability of the XGBR model. The work highlights the potential of integrating remote sensing data with machine learning techniques to address the challenges in agriculture.

Keywords: Remote sensing, Agriculture, Winter wheat, Production estimation, Terra MODIS, Machine learning, NDVI, Decision rule, XGBoost Regressor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wheat is one of the major cereal crops worldwide and plays an essential role in nutrition, food security, global trade, and the economy. Wheat is the primary source of calories for a large population and is considered a staple in regions like Europe, Asia, and North America. Timely and accurate production estimation is crucial for planning and managing resources, as well as for formulating policies. Conventional yield estimation methods rely on field samples and manual surveys, making the process resource-intensive, laborious, and time-consuming. Moreover, it limits the study region in terms of spatial and temporal coverage. Hence, an efficient, data-driven approach is needed that integrates data on key parameters from multiple sources to predict wheat yield prior to harvest.

Remote sensing has revolutionized the field by providing cutting-edge tools and techniques for collecting, analyzing, and monitoring a wide range of agricultural information. Advances in sensors and data processing have

further enhanced RS capabilities. High-resolution imagery at 10-metre spatial resolution, collected by modern satellites such as Sentinel and Landsat, allows for a detailed analysis of the focus area. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) enable real-time monitoring of large areas.

The present study aims to integrate RS-based information and meteorological time-series data spanning over two decades to predict wheat production across five major wheat-growing states in India. Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, Rajasthan, and Bihar were selected as study areas as they accounted for more than 75% of the national wheat output in 2022-23 [1]. The states have noticeable variations in soil types, vegetation, weather conditions, temperatures, resource availability, and implemented policies. Hence, the dataset formed captures this difference.

Recent studies have investigated multi-sensor data fusion (multispectral, thermal, and RGB) in conjunction with machine learning algorithms. A set of standard parameters was consistently employed across various crop types, including the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) [2-4], which is used to evaluate crop health, as well as climatic variables like temperature, humidity, and rainfall, and soil-related features, namely soil moisture and soil type. These parameters were observed to directly

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influence crop growth. Additional parameters used in the literature include Leaf Area Index (LAI), Radar Vegetation Index (RVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index, green-red ratio index [3], green-blue ratio index, solar radiation, minimum and maximum temperatures, and vapour pressure deficit. The machine learning and deep learning models frequently cited in prior research encompass Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest Regression (RFR), Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT), Multilayer Perceptron, Artificial Neural Networks [5], and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), alongside classification techniques such as K-means clustering and maximum likelihood estimation.

The connection between RS and GIS enables a more comprehensive approach to prediction. GIS integrates spatial data to facilitate the analysis of agricultural land in relation to climatic and environmental factors. In addition, combining remote sensing data with in-situ measurements enhances the robustness and accuracy of models during estimation. This synergy not only boosts agricultural productivity but also supports sustainability. The objective of this work is to compare tree-based methods on a dataset created for five major Indian states.

II. STUDY AREA & DATASET

A. STUDY AREA

The study was conducted for five states in India, namely Uttar Pradesh (UP), Madhya Pradesh (MP), Haryana (HR), Rajasthan (RJ) and Bihar (BR), which are part of the country’s Wheat Belt (Fig. 1). Uttar Pradesh contributes nearly 35% to the country’s wheat output, followed by Madhya Pradesh (19%), Haryana (9%), Rajasthan (11%), and Bihar (~6%) [6]. The variations observed in the study region with respect to climate, ecological resources, meteorological parameters, and water availability contribute to the generalizability of the research.

Fig. 1. Study Area

B. DATASET OVERVIEW

The study utilized remote sensing derived data, meteorological data and production data. Data were acquired for a period of 22 years, ranging from 2003 to 2025. Dataset included:

- Terra MODIS data – RS-derived vegetative indices (like NDVI, LAI), soil moisture, and land acreage.
- Meteorological data – Temperature, precipitation, and humidity [7]
- Production data – Wheat production data available on the Unified Portal of Agricultural Statistics (UPAg), Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Government of India [8].

NDVI was the primary input used to derive other remote sensing-based parameters. As wheat grows, the NDVI value ranges from 0.1 to 0.9.

Fig. 2(a). NDVI Chart of Uttar Pradesh

Fig. 2(b). NDVI Chart of Madhya Pradesh

Fig. 2(c). NDVI Chart of Haryana

Fig. 2(d). NDVI Chart of Rajasthan

Fig. 2(e). NDVI Chart of Bihar

Fig. 2(a), Fig. 2(b), Fig. 2(c), Fig. 2(d), and Fig. 2(e) depict the NDVI values for the five Indian states. As the crop grows, the value varies, i.e., it initially increases, gradually reaches a maximum value, and then decreases.

III. METHODOLOGY

There are various approaches to predicting production. One approach is to use ground-truth values, since they ensure that the area covered in the study is truly wheat-specific. The other is to mark training points on the map, then filter for wheat-producing areas. Each method has its challenges, such as the unavailability of ground-truth data in the former and the difficulty of identifying wheat crop in satellite imagery for classification in the latter. Therefore, an alternative approach, called 'Decision-based classification for wheat,' was used.

A. DECISION-BASED CLASSIFICATION FOR WHEAT

Decision rule-based classification takes in a set of predefined logical conditions on NDVI based on wheat phenology. Wheat is a rabi crop sown in the month of October and harvested in April. According to the crop's phenological stages (Table 1), NDVI maps in Google Earth Engine typically show an initial increase in NDVI values from 0.1 to 0.7, followed by a gradual decrease. This pattern reflects the crop's growth from seedling to grain maturity and helps distinguish wheat from other crops. The greener

the crop, the higher its NDVI. This implies that when the seed is sown, NDVI values will be low, and as the crop reaches maturity and turns golden in colour, NDVI values will be lower.

Table 1. Wheat phenology in terms of NDVI values

Stage	NDVI Range	Remark	Month
Germination & seeding	0.1 - 0.2	Low NDVI	Oct – Nov
Tillering	0.3 - 0.5	Increasing NDVI	Nov-Dec
Stem elongation & Booting	May exceed 0.7	Peak NDVI	January
Heading & Flowering	May starts lowering from its peak value	Plateau or slight decline in NDVI	February
Grain Filling	0.5 - 0.6	Declining NDVI	March
Ripening & harvesting	Below 0.3	Low NDVI	March-April

The wheat map created from NDVI values will subsequently be used to extract LAI and thermal anomalies in wheat-growing regions within the study areas. Each state has a different production intensity based on soil type, meteorological conditions, farmers' resources, policy implementation, etc. Therefore, creating a single shape file for each state is not an efficient way to identify wheat with the highest possible precision. Hence, each state is divided into four major categories, namely high, medium, low, and very low, based on wheat intensity.

In each map, wheat-growing areas are represented in green and non-wheat areas are highlighted in yellow. Wheat maps of all five states were analyzed. However, for representation purposes, wheat masks from the 2018-19 crop season are illustrated to make readers realize the wheat distribution of five states. Wheat maps generated for each state for the crop season 2018-19 are illustrated in Fig. 3(a), Fig. 3(b), Fig. 3(c), Fig. 3(d), and Fig. 3(e). VEDAS was used for wheat maps validation [9].

Fig. 3(a) illustrates the wheat spread in Uttar Pradesh during the 2018-19 crop season. The map indicates that the wheat-producing regions are concentrated mainly in the central, western, and eastern parts of the state, suggesting these areas benefit from favourable conditions, including adequate water supply and suitable agro-climatic conditions for efficient winter wheat cultivation. Most of the wheat in UP is cultivated in the Ganga-Ghaghara plain, which is characterized by well-developed irrigation systems and nutrient-rich alluvial soils [10].

Fig. 3(b) shows the wheat cultivation areas of Madhya Pradesh for the crop season 2018-19. Wheat was mainly observed in the northern and central parts of the state, including Gwalior, Morena, Vidisha, Hoshangabad, and

parts of Bhopal and Sehore. The observed wheat spread aligns with the Malwa plateau and Narmada Valley regions, where irrigation facilities and soil quality are superior to those in other regions [11]. On the other hand, the southern and south-western regions of the state were found to have relatively lower wheat intensity.

Fig. 3(a). Wheat Map of Uttar Pradesh

proportion of non-wheat regions than wheat-growing areas. These non-wheat zones comprise deserts, hilly terrain, or semi-arid regions that have limiting climatic conditions and soil and water resources for wheat cultivation. Key districts identified for wheat production include Sri Ganganagar, Hanumangarh, Alwar, Kota, Bharatpur, and Bundi [12].

Fig. 3(c). Wheat Map of Haryana

Fig. 3(b). Wheat Map of Madhya Pradesh

Fig. 3(b) shows the wheat cultivation areas of Madhya Pradesh for the crop season 2018-19. Wheat was mainly observed in the northern and central parts of the state, including Gwalior, Morena, Vidisha, Hoshangabad, and parts of Bhopal and Sehore. The observed wheat spread aligns with the Malwa plateau and Narmada Valley regions, where irrigation facilities and soil quality are superior to those in other regions [11]. On the other hand, the southern and southwestern regions of the state were found to have relatively lower wheat intensity.

Fig. 3(c) is the wheat map of Haryana for the 2018-19 crop season, which clearly shows the dense, extensive wheat production across nearly the entire state. Sirsa, Fatehabad, Jind, Kaithal, Kurukshetra, Ambala and Karnal emerged as the major wheat-producing districts of Haryana.

Fig. 3(d) illustrates the wheat map for Rajasthan for the crop season 2018-19. It is noted that the state has a greater

Fig. 3(d). Wheat Map of Rajasthan

Fig. 3(e). Wheat Map of Bihar

Fig. 3(e) depicts the wheat mask of Bihar for the crop season 2018-19. The map clearly indicates that the central, western, and northern regions of Bihar predominantly contribute to wheat production. These regions include Bhojpur, Buxar, Saran, Nalanda, and Patna. Rivers such as the Ganga and Gandak facilitate irrigation in these regions, while the alluvial soils enhance fertility [13].

B. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Fig. 4 shows the methodological flow of the study. Firstly, remote sensing derived data, meteorological data and yield data from various sources were acquired. Next, the data were preprocessed and missing values were removed. To make the data consistent across the datasets, scaling was applied to bring all parameters to the same temporal (16-day interval) and spatial (500-meter) resolutions. The final dataset was created by merging all the parameters in a structured format. A train-test split of 80:20 was taken, where 80% of the data was used for training the models, and the remaining 20% was used to test the models. To validate the models, the error percentages were calculated. In addition, evaluation metrics such as RMSE, MAE, R² Score and MAPE were computed. Finally, the results achieved from the models were visualized using various plots. These visuals provide better insights into the limitations and strengths of each model.

Fig. 4. Methodological Flow of Study

The ML models used in the study are Decision Tree Regressor, Random Forrest Regression, Extra Trees Regressor, and XGBoost Regressor. These regressors were selected for their robustness to overfitting and their ability to handle non-linear and heterogeneous data.

Fig. 5 presents the correlation heatmap of the input features for the wheat production estimation dataset. The selected features show weak correlations with each other, so they can be used to predict the target variable, i.e., production.

Fig. 5. Correlation Heatmap

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. PERFORMANCE METRICS

Table 2 summarizes the performance of the four regression models viz. Decision Tree, Random Forest, Extra Trees, and XGBoost using four statistical evaluation metrics MAE, RMSE, R² Score and MAPE, for wheat production estimation using remote sensing and meteorological data. These metric values are based on the combined data of all five states.

Table 2. Performance metrics

Evaluation Metric	Algorithms			
	DTR	RFR	ETR	XGBR
MAE	1878338.35	1417295.27	1342476.41	991596.44
RMSE	2221773.75	1634856.56	1591842.44	1160665.17
R ²	0.955	0.976	0.977	0.987
MAPE	10.33%	8.26%	7.43%	5.60%

The results show that XGBoost outperforms other models, achieving the lowest MAE and RMSE and the highest R² score, which implies a superior ability to capture underlying patterns in the dataset. Extra trees and random forest models performed better than the decision tree model. The high error percentage and the lowest R² score of the decision tree indicate possible overfitting or under fitting issues that differ across regions.

Table 3 shows the state-wise RMSE values for each of the four models. The state-wise wheat production in crop season 2024-25 was 35736220.8 by Uttar Pradesh, 23511672 by Madhya Pradesh, 11356848.64 by Haryana, 10946233.6 by Rajasthan and 6931875.72 by Bihar.

Table 3. State-wise RMSE Values

State	RMSE values of Algorithms			
	DTR	RFR	ETR	XGBR
Uttar Pradesh	3654032.11	2805767	2800852	2009246
Madhya Pradesh	2929140.39	1879843	1806109	1329949
Haryana	1191568.64	879592.2	825355.7	654316.1
Rajasthan	914490.53	825751.1	791422.8	584042.7
Bihar	702460.08	549524.5	505420.7	400809.9

B. RESULT VISUALIZATION

To visualize the results, line plots, residual plots, radar plots, error box plots, and error percentage graphs were used.

Fig. 6(a), Fig. 6(b), Fig. 6(c) and Fig. 6(d) present line plots of decision tree, random forest, extra trees and XGBoost, respectively, where the blue line indicates the actual production and the orange line indicates the production predicted by the model.

The line plot of the Decision Tree Regressor model was rigid and step-like. It can be observed that the decision tree in this study captured the general trends and detected prominent changes in production across the training samples, but also exhibited overfitting. Irrespective of the different parameters like NDVI, LAI, etc., used with varying values during the crop cycle, the decision tree regressor generates the same value of production, which is an output variable for a set of records. The values predicted by DTR are discrete.

Fig. 6(a). Line Plot of Decision Tree Regressor

Fig. 6(b). Line Plot of Random Forest Regressor

The plots of Extra Trees and Random Forest exhibited smoother patterns compared to the decision tree. ETR more effectively captured the transition in production across high-, medium-, and low-production regions than either the decision tree or the random forest. This improved performance stems from the increased randomness introduced in the splits during the implementation of extra

trees. The ETR model predicted production values that closely matched the actual production in Fig. 6(c), particularly around the 60th test sample, where predictions were quite close to the true values, demonstrating strong predictive accuracy. The plot for the RFR model also aligned quite closely with the actual values. However, for approximately the first fifteen samples, the model was found to overestimate production. Overall, the model captured both high- and low-production zones throughout the test dataset. This indicates that the random forest outperformed the decision tree, highlighting the benefits of ensemble methods such as better generalization, reduced overfitting, and increased robustness.

Fig. 6(c). Line Plot of Extra Trees Regressor

Fig. 6(d). Line Plot of XGBoost Regressor

The plot of XGBoost shows close alignment between actual and predicted values, indicating high predictive accuracy across all regions, i.e., high, medium, and low production. This pattern of close alignment is consistent across all test samples, revealing the model’s ability to generalize well to the given dataset. Also, because there are fewer instances of under- or over prediction, the overall reliability of the model is unaffected. This also validates the model’s ability to learn from nonlinear data.

Fig. 7(a), Fig. 7(b), Fig. 7(c), and Fig. 7(d) present the residual plots for the decision tree, random forest, extra trees, and XGBoost models, respectively.

Fig. 7(a). Residual Plot of Decision Tree Regressor

Fig. 7(b). Residual Plot of Random Forest Regressor

Fig. 7(c). Residual Plot of Extra Trees Regressor

Fig. 7(d). Residual Plot of XGBoost Regressor

A single decision tree is a model characterized by high variance because it learns complex rules and attempts to fit the training data perfectly. This tendency can lead to overfitting when the tree is deep and to under fitting when it is shallow, often resulting in missed patterns in the data. Thus, DTR predictions can be non-smooth, and residual plots often contain discrete points because the output remains constant for data points within the same leaf.

In the residual plot of the Decision Tree Regressor, as observed in Fig. 7(a), residuals are broadly dispersed around the horizontal zero line, indicating that the model both under predicts and over predicts the production values. A few notably high residuals are visible, suggesting that the predictions are not highly accurate. Consequently, the model demonstrates inconsistent predictions across the test dataset due to overfitting. The error percentage achieved by the DTR model was found ranging from 8.35% to 12.45% across different states.

Random Forest and Extra Trees use bagging, which reduces variance by training many independent trees separately on the dataset and then averaging their predictions. Thus, the residuals obtained from the random forest predictions are slightly improved over those from the decision tree. Even the clusters of residuals can be seen about two production values in the plot, both above and below the horizontal line, indicating over prediction and under prediction. However, the residuals of the random forest are not perfectly random, which indicates the model’s bias. Still, the performance of random forest is reasonably good, but is found struggling slightly with extreme data values. The error percentage achieved by the random forest ranged from 6.03% to 8.84% across different states.

The residuals calculated based on the extra trees model predictions are found to be quite similar to those of random forest residuals. The model fits better in the medium production range. Moreover, residual points are more widely distributed in ETR than in RFR. The error percentage achieved by extra trees ranged from 6.96% to 8.39% across states.

XGBoost is a method that uses the boosting technique to obtain the final result. A tree is built, and its errors are calculated. Then another tree is built to handle these errors specifically. As a result, the bias is reduced because boosting targets at points where the model is failing, i.e., the points where the residual value is high. This can be observed in Fig. 7(d), where the residuals are tightly clustered around the horizontal line, indicating a balanced distribution with fewer outliers than the other three models. The error percentage achieved in XGBoost ranged from 5.29% to 5.76% for different states.

Fig. 8 presents the normalized radar plot where four models, DTR, RFR, ETR, and XGBR, are compared on the basis of three evaluation metrics – RMSE, MAE, and R^2 score. The Decision Tree performed poorly across all metrics, as indicated by its low scores shown in blue at the centre of the chart. Both Random Forest and Extra Trees showed moderate performances, scoring between 0.5 and 0.7 on all metrics. Their proximity on the plot suggested

similar performance levels. The triangle of the XGBoost model occupied the largest area in the chart, with values close to 1 across all metrics, indicating minimal RMSE and MAE and a high R^2 score. This demonstrates that XGBoost outperformed the other models in the study.

Normalized Radar Plot of RMSE, MAE, and R^2

Fig. 8. Radar Plot

Fig. 9 represents the error box plots of the four models. Among all, the box plot of XGBoost follows all three characteristics of an ideal box plot. This shows the model is relatively accurate throughout the dataset, as the size of whiskers is small, over-predicting or under-predicting is less in XGB because the median lies near zero, and the error distribution is concentrated in a small area as the box is of small size.

Fig. 9. Error Box Plots

Fig. 10 presents the overall error percentages for each model. Results revealed that the DTR model obtained the highest error rate of 10.3%, followed by the RFR model (8.3%), ETR model (7.4%), and XGBoost model (5.6%). Among all the models tested, XGBoost achieved the lowest error rate, indicating higher predictive accuracy.

This comparison sheds light on the effects of moving

from a simple model, like a decision tree, where a single tree is responsible for making the decision, to a complex model, like XGBoost, where trees are iteratively built to reduce residuals for data points. Consequently, the error percentage continues to decrease as we progress from the decision tree (10.3%) to XGBoost (5.6%), then to random forest (8.3%) and extra trees (7.4%).

Fig. 10. Error Percentage Graphs

C. RESULT INTERPRETATION

As revealed by the line plots, the DTR model exhibited notable divergence and significant fluctuations between actual and predicted values, as single-tree predictions deviate more from the actual values. RFR and ETR models outperformed DTR by more accurately capturing the overall trend, though some deviations remained, as averaging multiple trees smoothens prediction deviations. On the other hand, both variance and bias are minimised in XGBoost because of sequential tree building. The predicted values are closely aligned with actual production figures and show minimal gaps between lines, indicating the model's high reliability on real-world data.

As observed from the residual plots, the DTR model exhibited a large spread of residuals, indicating poor generalisation and high prediction errors. The RFR and ETR models were slightly better than DTR, as the residuals were more symmetrically spread around the zero line; hence, their performance can be labelled as moderately better. The residuals in XGBoost were the closest and tightly clustered around the zero line, indicating the most accurate predictions with the least error among all models. The scatter of residuals in the residual plots indicates that the features and the target variable do not exhibit a linear relationship. Thus, it cannot be approximated by a simple orthogonal decision boundary, as a single estimator will be unable to capture the patterns. XGBoost is capable of handling it effectively due to its boosting mechanism, in which it builds trees by minimising error.

The lower the value of RMSE, the lower the value of MAE, and the higher the R^2 score, the better is the model's performance. Model performance was tested for the combined production data of all five states, viz. UP, MP, Haryana, Rajasthan and Bihar. The cumulative wheat

production for all five states in the rabi season of 2024-25 was reported as 88482850.7, as per UPAg. The XGBR model achieved the lowest RMSE of 1160665.17 and MAE of 991596.44, and the highest R^2 of 0.987, followed by ETR (RMSE = 1591842.44, MAE = 1342476.41, and R^2 = 0.977) and RFR (RMSE = 1634856.56, MAE = 1417295.27, and R^2 = 0.976). Conversely, the DTR model achieved the highest RMSE of 2221773.75, the highest MAE of 1878338.35, and the lowest R^2 score of 0.955. This variation in performance measures is due to the design and working principle of each model. A decision tree relies on a single tree, which makes it prone to overfitting and high variance. Random forest reduces variance by averaging across multiple trees, which improves stability during prediction, but residual errors are not actively corrected, so bias remains. When more randomness is introduced in the random forest for feature selection, extra trees are created. The variance decreases, but randomness may increase bias, which may affect prediction accuracy. Using boosting to build trees sequentially, where each new tree corrects the errors of the previous ones, reduces bias and variance. As a result, the boosting method performs better than random forests, extra trees, and decision trees.

In addition, XGBR showed the best error box plot among all the models, as it satisfied all three conditions for an ideal error distribution. One, low median error where the center is near zero. As the error decreases with each iteration, the median error approaches zero. For the other three models, the prediction is biased because of either a single tree model or averaging, which stabilizes predictions, but residual biases are not corrected. Second, a small interquartile range (IQR) means variability in error must be low. So, in the XGBR model, learning rate, regularization, and controlled tree depth lead to stable and consistent predictions, which result in a tight interquartile range. Whereas the decision tree, which is a high-variance model, produces errors over a large spread, hence, the IQR is wide. Random forest reduces variability by averaging, but randomness during tree building results in a moderate spread in the IQR. Extra trees have additional randomness, which can at times cause the IQR to be greater than that of RFR. Third, short whiskers so that extreme outliers are less. The iterative process of XGBoost progressively corrects extreme residuals, so the deviation decreases and the whiskers shorten. A decision tree can give large errors on unseen patterns, which creates long whiskers. Averaging in random forests and extra trees reduces extreme values to some extent but does not specifically target extreme outliers.

V. CONCLUSION

This work aimed to attain an accurate estimate of wheat production by integrating remote sensing based data, production data, and meteorological data. The study area included five major Indian states, namely Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan and Haryana. A well-curated dataset from various Terra MODIS data products like MODIS/061/MOD09A1 for NDVI, MODIS/061/MCD15A3H for leaf area index,

MODIS/061/MOD14A2 for thermal anomaly, along with soil moisture data from GLDAS - NASA/GLDAS/V021/NOAH/G025/T3H, meteorological data, i.e., temperature, precipitation and humidity from the visual crossing website and statistical data of production from UPAg was compiled over the duration of 2003 to 2025. All the parameters were explicitly aligned spatially at 500 meters and temporally at 8 days. Four machine learning tree-based models, namely Decision Tree Regressor (DTR), Random Forest Regressor (RFR), Extra Trees Regressor (ETR) and XGBoost Regressor (XGBR), were successfully implemented to predict the wheat production.

A decision rule-based classification method was employed to identify wheat and non-wheat areas across five Indian states, utilizing a set of pre-defined logical conditions on NDVI that corresponded to wheat phenology. A correlation heatmap was generated to identify the relationship among the parameters. The performance metrics, such as MAPE, RMSE, and R^2 , along with diagnostic plots like line plot, residual plot, radar plot, box plot, and error percentage graph, were created to evaluate and compare the performance of each model on the combined wheat production data across all five states, viz. UP, MP, Haryana, Rajasthan and Bihar.

The collective wheat production of all five states in the rabi season of 2024-25, as per UPAg statistics, was reported at 88482850.7. The findings demonstrate that XGBoost performed best, with an RMSE of 1160665.17, followed by Extra Trees with an RMSE of 1591842.44, Random Forest with an RMSE of 1634856.56, and Decision Tree with the highest RMSE of 2221773.75. The average error percentages for the Decision Tree, Random Forest, Extra Trees, and XGBoost models were 10.3%, 8.3%, 7.4%, and 5.6%, respectively. This highlights that models such as decision tree, random forest, and extra trees may struggle with correlated or high-dimensional features, whereas XGBoost optimally weights them. The iterative process of boosting performs better than bagging and single-tree based models.

The results emphasize the power of integrating remote sensing data with machine learning techniques and agro-meteorological data to predict production before the harvest season.

VI. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE SCOPE

Although the results are promising, the model can be further improved by incorporating ground data. It should be noted that the entire study was conducted without a single field visit, which may be considered both, a major disadvantage as well as a major advantage of the research work reported in this study. The work is advantageous because, without deploying financial support and human resources, an error rate of 5.6% to 10.3% was achieved in production. However, due to the lack of ground-truth support, the possibility that errors are higher than those reported for some districts cannot be ruled out. Therefore, it is advised to use the wheat maps presented in Fig. 3(a) to 3(e) as reference maps with discretion.

The methodology reported in this paper can be adopted by researchers to predict wheat production for their area of interest. The study provides a scalable approach that can be utilized to predict crop production and applied to other crops and regions. Expanding or refining the area of interest will help stakeholders to monitor food security on a large scale. Integrating multi-sensor data, such as SAR data, with MODIS will help overcome atmospheric effects like cloud cover. This will improve the robustness of the model and ensure it continues to work accurately under cloudy conditions. By integrating weather data with crop health, a system can predict production losses before they occur, thereby enabling precision agriculture in real-time.

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